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STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

AC

Popular Traditions on the Feast of Baptism of the Lord in Romania How they were Assimilated and Shaped in the Church¹

Rev. Gabriel Pisteaa*

ABSTRACT

The Feast of the Baptism of the Lord was celebrated on the same date as the Feast of Christmas, 6 January, until the 4th-5th centuries. That's why the two feasts have a great connection, and their traditions are similar. In this study, we will analyze the ethnographic elements inserted in the popular memory of the Romanian people, not only held on the Feast of Epiphany but also referring in particular to the Epiphany service or the Great Sanctification of Water.

Keywords: The Feast of the Baptism of the Lord, the Feast of Christmas, the Great Sanctification of Water, popular tradition, ethnography.

In this study, we will analyze the ethnographic elements inserted in the popular memory of the Romanian people, and not only held on the occasion of the Epiphany, referring in particular to the Epiphany service. First, we will enter the world of carols dedicated to this act of the Saviour, and we will analyze their themes. We will then look at the customs or traditions that include the two essential elements of the service of Epiphany: the cross and the Basil. In the third part, we will look at the meaning of the Great Sanctification of Water, the Holy Water, or the 'Jordan' – as it is known in the local dialect – from an ethnographic point of view, and at the popular customs that take place on this occasion. In the last section, we will present the main folk customs in our country that are celebrated on the feast of Epiphany, such as "kiraleisa", "iordănitul", "lipiul", "baptism of horses", "boura", "gogorița", "guarding the fountains", "Saint Ion's doll", "ardeasca" etc.²

Carols dedicated to the Feast of Epiphany

Since the Feast of Epiphany has long been celebrated with the Feast of the Nativity, the custom of caroling has spread throughout the period from 24th of December to the 6th of January. Thus, in the tradition of the Christian peoples, there are many carols on the theme of the Baptism of the Lord in Jordan. Their text doesn't follow the biblical episode of the event from Jordan but rather presents the actual practice of baptism, portraying Jesus as a baby brought to baptism by his mother. The carol verses extend the event of the Nativity as

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the Mother of the Child is depicted in the same state of flight, in fear of the Jews, which is interpreted as Jesus' mother refusing to let the Jews baptize Him into their law. In the caroling tradition from the Romanian region of Muntenia, the Mother of God and the Child climb a mountain together. They are followed by St John, who leads them to a place where three rivers flow: one of water, one of milk, and one of myrrh. Despite the biblical event, the text of these carols has influenced the iconographic tradition.

In many icons, Jesus is depicted as a child at his Baptism. In one depiction of the icon of the Nativity of the Lord, the holy infant's bath is described, with two women pouring water into the font where the Lord is, highlighting both the Nativity and the act of Baptism.³

Popular tradition gives other connotations to the biblical event and the iconographic program from which it is primarily inspired. The three rivers represent the initiation of the Child, referring to the three sacraments of initiation into the Church. The milk element was present in the Western ritual of the Sacrament of Baptism, as St Ambrose of Milan presents it to us. The text of the carols suggests, on the one hand, that Jesus receives a name and is consecrated. On the other hand, it shows us that through the elements of water, myrrh, and milk, the material is sanctified because the divine Child has entered into them. Also, from the text of the carols for Epiphany, we get the idea that the infant Jesus also had a godfather at his baptism, namely St John the Baptist:

Dar nănaș pe cine cheamă / Tot pe Ioan Sântion / Nănașul lui Dumnezeu” (“But whom does the godfather call / Still John the Baptist / God's godfather”).

This role of the Saviour's godfather is widespread in Balkan folklore and other areas such as southern Italy and Corsica. The Baptist earns his role as Godfather of the Lord following a meeting of the saints, to which he appears on a beautiful horse. He acquires this status by being the oldest of them all. The Carol text overturns the values, placing John as more significant than God. A carol from northern Macedonia depicts the Lord, after his baptism, kneeling before John.⁴

The text of another carol, Hunedoara from Romania, from the area's repertoire, depicts Saint Sunday, who is called by the Mother of God to baptize Jesus as godmother. On the way, she stops at a fountain where she picks three flowers, suggesting the fulfillment of ritual gestures. When she arrives at the place of baptism, she finds that the Child has been baptized by St. John, which causes her great sorrow, and the Saint wants to kill herself:

Găsi Fiu mic botezat / Tot de Ionul, Sânt Ionu, / Ea de ciudă și de-obidă / Dete-n mare să se-nece” (“She finds her little Son baptized / All by John, St. John, / She for sorrow and sadness / She longs to drown herself”).

To accomplish this liturgical ritual act, we see the Saint herself following a purification ritual through washing.⁵

The custom of caroling at Epiphany is relatively new. The first references are found in Moldova and northern Bukovina, where we get Epiphany songs from the 20th century. An Epiphany carol from the Botoșani area is handed down by Elena Niculiță-Voronca. It

faithfully respects the biblical episode of the Baptism of the Lord, which she describes in carol verses⁶. Also, the walking with the star or the globe⁷ continued from Christmas to Epiphany. In the village of Solca, for example, the masked men would go to people's houses every Epiphany, making a man with straw and rags, who was supposed to be the finacé of the unmarried daughters of the hosts. This custom of walking around with masks was also practiced in the county of Bistrița-Năsăud on the night of the Epiphany. In the town of Blaj, the children, gathered in groups, would walk around with a carol, performing various scenes on the theme of the Baptism of the Lord. In the Lutheran villages, they walked with the "beaua", a custom that replaced the walking with the Holy Cross on Epiphany Eve by the priests⁸. The folklorist Traian Herseni tells us that, in certain regions, on Epiphany Eve, the young lads gather to learn a carol called Aghiosul, which they will perform on Epiphany Day when they go to the river for the sanctification of the waters. It follows the biblical episode, depicting the moment of the Lord's baptism by St John, being a carol of ecclesiastical origin⁹. Caraman tells us that the custom of caroling at Epiphany is also a tradition of the Greek and other Eastern European people¹⁰. From the Hellenic area, we have the carol of the Feast of Lights, entitled *Σήμερα τα φώτα...*

Holy Cross and Basil – traditional elements of the Feast of Epiphany

The most essential elements of the Epiphany service are the Holy Cross and the Basil. These have taken on many connotations in the Romanian popular tradition. We know the custom of making ice crosses, which are placed on the day of the Epiphany, around where the Great Water Sanctification occurs. If this occurs in flowing water, huge rivers or the Black Sea, it is customary for the officiant to throw a cross into the water and the young people to swim towards it. The one who catches it first is blessed with health and help from God. The Aromanians, for example, are digging a large hole before Epiphany, in which the priest throws the cross and the young people jump after it into the cold water to catch it, saying: "En i Ordani (Into the Jordan) ... and happy birthday to you!" These young men, called "liguciori", carry this cross around to people's houses all day, receiving "tips." If the Great Sanctification of the Water was celebrated at the river, the thrown cross was caught by a child, who then walked with the priest to people's houses, carrying the cross caught in the river. The making of ice crosses is documented in the 19th century. Some predictions were made from them. For example, in the village of Ruginoasa, it was said that if the ice on the cross flowed, that year would be good. In the mountainous area of Bukovina, fir trees were planted around the ice crosses, and hay straw was placed under the priest's feet, on which he knelt. At the end of the service, people would take branches from the bramble and hay straw for the health of the animals¹¹. This custom is still preserved today in the village of Părâuți in Suceava, where the struggle to acquire those "sanctified" hay straws is more significant than that to obtain the Holy Great Water.

Regarding Basil, an ethnographic tradition tells us that the people who participated in the Baptism of the Lord brought Basil, with which they covered Christ. Thus, the Basil remained in the church, and the priest consecrated the water with it. To this respect, testimonies of the peasants received from their ancestors tell us that the Lord received the name of Christ at the Baptism. Until then, He was called Basil, which, from the Latin word Basilicum and the Russian word Vaselioc, translates as Basil. Another tradition tells us that the Basil flower helped St Helena find the Lord's Cross. Basil grew on the spot where the

cross was hidden, indicating its presence. From this, we can see the resemblance, almost to the point of identification, according to the elders, of the Cross with the Basil, without which the water cannot be made holy. In Bukovina, it is said that the Basil was made from the Lord's blood that dripped from the Cross, also representing the tears of the Mother of God. That is why when it is harvested, it is placed at icons or in clean places. In some parts of our country, Basil has acquired a magical practice: unmarried girls take from the Basil that the priest brings to each person's house with the traditional Epiphany visit and place it on their bedside on Epiphany Eve, hoping that they will dream of their sweetheart. With the help of Basil and Marigold, love spells can be made¹². In other areas, unmarried girls pluck Basil threads from the priest's sprigs; they carefully see where the priest first steps into the house and take earth from that spot. Some put the Basil threads dipped in the Holy Water and the earth under their pillow, and others made their bed and went to sleep right where the priest first stepped when he entered the house¹³.

The Great Sanctification of the Water, the Great Water, or the "Jordan" – popular customs

The highlight of the Feast of Epiphany is the Great Sanctification of Water, which gives birth to the Great Holy Water, or "Jordan," as it is popularly called. This moment has gained, over time, remarkable widespread significance in Romanian villages. The Epiphany represents, in the old traditions and customs, the moment when heaven opens and everything is sanctified, the pure man having the opportunity to talk to God on the night of the Epiphany. Anyone who keeps vigil on this night will be healthy, he and his whole household will be healthy, and no evil will touch him. The guardian angel becomes a discoverer of the future, telling pious girls or daughters whom they will marry or be married to. Simion Florea Marian notes that the animals catch the human voice this night, and pure men can hear the semantron beaten in the sky. This supernatural atmosphere of the union of heaven and earth highlights the spiritual charge of this moment when all the creation is sanctified and renewed. The earth tastes the heavenly fragrance through the Holy Water. Everything is purified through baptism. The same ethnographer mentioned above gives us details about the preparation of the place where the consecration of the water will take place, as well as typical rules about what is chanted at this service. Besides the hymnography in the books of worship, he says other poems with religious themes are also sung in some areas, such as Banat. He also describes the crowd after the consecration of the waters, when they flock to take from the holy water, showing an impatience with the healing power of this miraculous water. The purpose of the hustle is that whoever takes the first of the holy water will be healthier than the others because the first water is purer than the one who takes the last. This belief was handed down from the ancestors.¹⁴

In his collection of traditions and customs from different parts of our country, Simion Florea Marian tells us that this sumptuous way of celebrating Epiphany was also done earlier. The author explains this in a testimony of Archdeacon Paul of Aleppo, who, following a visit to Moldavia and Wallachia with his Patriarch Macarius of Antioch between 1652 and 1660, records the following:

The crowds and the joy of the crowds in Wallachia at Epiphany surpass anything that happens at the courts of the greatest princes of Christianity, judging by what I have heard and seen. In the evening (now at noon or about noon), after the prayer over the water, the clergymen fill their pitchers or buckets with it, and,

dressing with the phelonion, take the crosses in their hands and go first to the palace of the landlord, whom they sprinkle each in turn and in a special way, and receive from him a beautiful gift; then they go to the local metropolitan, and from there to the houses of all the ministers and the wealthier citizens.... At last, we leave the Church so that the Patriarch can sink the cross in the river. The procession was formed first by the stewards two by two, with their symbols and flags with crosses on top, then those with torches, then the priests two by two, and finally the Patriarch with the Metropolitan. When the Patriarch with the cross in his hand arrived at the banks of the river, he found the water frozen, for the morning was cold. In the past, it was customary to pray over the water in the middle of the courtyard, but the landlord, being old and the cold too severe, this time, the prayer was made inside the palace. Now, the people had broken the ice, and the Patriarch plunged the Cross into the water three times, during which time a hymn was sung. After that, the crowd filled their pitchers from the river, and the priests immersed a significant number of children, some of whom froze; it pained us to hear the cries of the children, suffering from the ice and the cold... When the landlord kissed the Cross, a sign was given to the troops, and they discharged their muskets, thundering through the air, and we feared lest the Church should fall upon us; our ears were deafeningly deaf. From here, the Patriarch sprinkled the landlords in front. To be seen like spring flowers, in their bright clothes and wrapped in furs, which is considered an indispensable sign of richness... Let it be noted that all the great mountain landlords are beyond religious.¹⁵

Another custom relates to the fact that when the priest places the Cross in the rivers, the devils come out and flee to the fields, returning when it is no longer consecrated. That's why people don't leave clothes on fences to dry because the devils might take refuge in them. The laundry is not washed, nor is man during this period, according to the elders, since the waters are sanctified for a shorter or longer period, depending on the area. In Bukovina, Moldavia, Muntenia, and Transylvania, if the water is concentrated in the rivers, the young people throw themselves into the blessed water, hoping for health throughout the rest of the year. After people return home with the newly sanctified water, they sprinkle it on their cattle and the whole household, tasting the Great Holy Water themselves, believing that this will renew their baptism. They keep what's left because they believe this water never spoils and is a cure for various illnesses. Mothers whose infants died unbaptized take the Great Holy Water to their graves, pouring on them the figure of the Cross and reciting the baptismal formula¹⁶. Besides the element of water, in Transylvania, salt was also consecrated at Epiphany for the health of people and animals. A lump of sanctified salt was placed in the stable of the animals¹⁷.

Church dustpans or flags are dipped in holy water so that young people can throw themselves into the very place where they were washed. People decorate their water jugs with a candle, a bunch of Basil, and "scapes." At home, they also pour a little holy water into the barrels in the cellar. The remaining water and Basil are placed on the wall in a nail next to the icon. The water is tasted during the year when, for some reason, it is not possible to go to church or when a person is ill.¹⁸

Another custom connected with the time of the Sanctification of the Great Water is shooting. It is said that the Lord stood on the stone on which Adam's sin was written at Baptism.

During the Baptism, the slab broke, making a sound like a gun. Another testimony is, that at the time of the consecration of the waters, many devils were on the rivers, trying to disturb this moment. After the reading of the prayers, during the shooting, the ice breaks, drowning the devils.¹⁹

Various popular customs connected with Epiphany

The last part of this study will be dedicated to presenting some popular customs related to Epiphany, which bear specific names. The tradition of the priest going around the people's houses on Epiphany Eve with the anointing is common in all Romanian areas. This custom is also known as "walking with the chiraleisa," from the Greek expression "Κύριε Ελέησον," meaning "Lord have mercy." In some areas, groups of boys would surround houses or stables, ringing bells and shouting "Chiraleisa" or "Good fruit," with the connotation of a magical agricultural cult. The priest's visit with the Holy Water gives rise to many popular traditions, giving the moment a sacred connotation through the priest's presence and the objects he carries to sanctify the house: the cross, the Great Holy Water, and the Basil. In folk tradition, it is said that Adam had written the souls of men on a piece of paper, which he gave to the devil, and the devil put it in the water under a stone, holding all men captive from Adam. God sent St. Nicholas to hell to ask the devil who could remove the marks on that paper, and the devil told him only that man who would be born of a virgin and be baptized. This happened through the Person of the Saviour. At the time of the Baptism, He released three candles into the water, which burned the devil's paper, and thus the souls of men were set free. The devil, thinking that he would catch the Lord when He came to hell, made a chained chair, on which, however, He ended up sitting. The chair's chains are loosened throughout the year, but when the priest comes and shouts the "kiraleisa" at people's houses at Epiphany, the chains are strengthened again.²⁰

On Epiphany Eve, all the family members wait for the priest, without eating anything, to take the Great Holy Water. The priest enters the house, sprinkles everyone with the holy water, and gives them the Cross to kiss. The table is set, and the priest sits for a while and tastes some of the food for the good of the house. In the village of Vatra Moldoviței, after the priest leaves, the family members rush to sit in his place to have the priest's honor. In Moldavia, they eat after the priest leaves the house, and in parts of Bukovina, they eat only in the evening, as Epiphany Eve is considered a day of challenging fasting. From each house, the priest would take a piece of hemp, which was tied to his Basil, symbolizing that this hemp would catch all the evils of the house and would be dispersed. In the villages near Chernivtsi, as well as in the villages of Moldova, the priest was led by many men or children, with lighted candles and the cry "kiraleisa," up to the twelfth house²¹. Even today, the fathers of Putna Monastery, for example, go through the villages of Bukovina on Epiphany Eve, enjoying the same custom. In most places, the host greeted the priest with a lit candle, suggesting the light of Christ or St John. There were also more developed formulas, which the priest's companions said from house to house. We have such a testimony from the village of Vad, Maramureș, from the second half of the 19th century: "Chiraleisa Doamne / Popa cu feisa / Țură aluni / Preuteasa cu leasa / Diacu cu baltagu / Crăsnicu cu sacu / Țură aluni", and in the houses with girls to be married they added: „Căți cărbuni în vatră / Atâția pețitori la față / Țură aluni” ("How many coals in the hearth / So many suitors to the girl / Țură aluni"). Kiraleisa has become a form of carolling in the villages of Romania and Bessarabia.

Children walked with kiraleisa, a few houses behind the priest, receiving kolks, nuts, fruits or money²².

Epiphany Eve was called the Day of the Cross in Transylvania and Banat. On this day, the priests celebrated Divine Liturgy early in the morning and performed the service of the Holy Great Water in order to be able to go to the people's houses later - with the baptism, as they used to say in the mountains. If the parish was too big, the priest only went to the houses of the wealthier people, and the cantor went to the more distant houses. In Transylvania, the people went with the priest, each with a small tree in his hand²³. Weather forecasts were also made for the whole year on the Epiphany or the priest's visit. This phenomenon will persist throughout the year if it is a rainy Epiphany Eve. Rain will come from the direction towards which the priest first sprinkles the holy water. If Epiphany is beautiful or there is a shower, that year will be prosperous with a warm summer²⁴.

Another tradition of Epiphany was cooking "lipiului" (a cake). "Lipiul" was made from a dough whose components were put 9 times and cooked in the hearth. The loaf was placed under the door's threshold so that the priest could walk over it when he came with Eve. In the evening, after the girl had fasted all day, she would eat that cake after having made 101 prostrates, completely naked. After this ritual, the girls to be married listened to the part of the village where the dogs were barking or the roosters crowing to know where the future husband would come from. For the boys, lipiul meant seven little hens, named after seven girls they knew, one of whom could be their wife. They would randomly take one of the little necklaces, and which girl was inscribed on it could be his future bride.²⁵

On the day of the Epiphany, and sometimes on St. John's feast day, there is the custom of "iordănit." It started at the church door, where a group of young people sprinkled holy water on all the people. They would then go around the village with a bucket of holy water to sprinkle everyone, especially those named after St John the Baptist. From here, the custom began to be called "John's watering." Father Professor Ene Braniște, a great Roman liturgist, calls this tradition "a folkloric imitation of sacramental sprinkling."²⁶ The purpose of the sprinkling, sometimes even from the priest's chalice, was to have health and good luck in choosing a life partner.²⁷

Another popular tradition was the "baptism of horses", practiced in the Muntenia area. Young people would ride horses to the church door on Epiphany or St John's feast day. Here, the priest sprinkled them and the horses with holy water, making the baptism of these animals. After this, the young people would go to a large field where they would race each other. Today, beautifully decorated horses are harnessed to carts and brought to the Church to be sprinkled with holy water. That way, they will be hardworking and healthy all year round. This custom is also found among the Aromanians.²⁸

In the Dolj region, we find a custom, from the night of the Epiphany, called "guarding of the fountains". Young people stand guard over the wells this night so that impurities do not contaminate the water. The elders try the young men and come at night to watch them. They throw wheat or corn into the water if they catch them sleeping. So, in the morning, the whole band of young men had to clean the well until the water was pure and ready to be consecrated. In the morning, the young men, who had ensured the water was clean, would go around the village with bowls full of water, pouring it three times into the hands of the householders, who would wash their faces with the fresh water.²⁹

One last custom related to the Feast of Epiphany, which we mention, is called "ardeasca." Young men, boys, and girls, after the end of the service of the consecration of the Great Holy Water, took coals from the fire with which they lit the rifle ammunition and went to a large meadow where they built a big fire. Here, they danced around the fire, and when it was still going, they all jumped over it. The purpose of this custom was a spiritual purification of man from the evils he had accumulated throughout the year.³⁰

Conclusions

Popular traditions related to the Feast of the Baptism of the Lord are very rich in Romania, and they are inherited from our ancestors. Having become so much a part of people's consciousness, sometimes they have been given a more significant meaning than the Epiphany service itself. This is why folk traditions tend to be given greater importance than the main elements of the celebration. Some traditions have also found their way into the Church's public worship on the Feast of Epiphany, so much so that in traditional Romanian villages, they can generate severe disputes between priests and some believers who tend to emphasize these traditions and impose them to the detriment of the authentic spiritual experience of the redemptive event being celebrated.

As in other cases, the Church has assimilated some popular traditions of pagan origin, succeeding in making them Christian and giving them a meaning following its doctrine. At times, the struggle of the ministrants, through the process of catechesis, is to provide the faithful the correct doctrinal meaning of the Feast and to enlighten them regarding some popular traditions and their secondary role in the celebrated event.

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² For the popular traditions see also Necula 2004, p. 115-127.

³ Cepraga 1995, p. 51-53.

⁴ *Ibid*, p. 54-56.

⁵ *Ibid*, p. 142-156.

⁶ Niculiță-Voronca 1998, p. 55.

⁷ See also Adăscăliței 1978, p. 773-779.

⁸ Cojocaru 2012, p. 520-523.

⁹ Herseni 1997, p. 5.

¹⁰ Caraman 1983, p. 262-264.

¹¹ Cojocaru 2012, p. 526-527.

¹² Niculiță-Voronca 1998, p. 98-99.

¹³ Cojocaru 2012, p. 512.

¹⁴ Marian 1994, p. 146-150.

¹⁵ Hașdeu 1865, p. 92-93; Marian 1994, p. 150-151.

¹⁶ Marian 1994, p. 151-155.

¹⁷ Cojocaru 2012, p. 524-528.

¹⁸ Rădulescu-Codin and D. Mihalache 1909, p. 15-17.

¹⁹ Niculiță-Voronca 1998, p. 251-252.

²⁰ *Ibid*, p. 248.

²¹ *Ibid*, p. 250.

²² Cojocaru 2012, p. 508-518.

²³ Marian 1994, p. 127-133.

²⁴ Pistolea 2013, p. 159.

²⁵ Cojocaru 2012, p. 523.

²⁶ Braniște 2015, p. 304.

²⁷ Cojocaru 2012, p. 528-530.

²⁸ *Ibid* p. 530-531.

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